

GLOBALIZATION AND THE TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN DEVELOPING SOFTWARE SOLUTION FOR APPAREL INDUSTRY

Author(s)*: Ana-Maria APETREI (Married GULEI)
Position: PhD Student
University: Technical University Gheorghe Asachi -Iasi
Address: Bulevardul Profesor Dimitrie Mangeron 67, Iasi 700050
Email: anamariagulei12@gmail.com
Webpage: <https://www.tuiasi.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The objective of the paper is to highlight the importance of Total Quality Management (TQM) in software development in the context of globalization of the apparel industry sector.*

Prior Work: Analysis of existing reports for apparel industry status and trends, analysis of the existing software solutions developed dedicated to apparel sector, study of the literature specialized literature and articles that develops the subject of TQM.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Brief literature review with focus on TQM model and its successful implementations, context analysis in European Union (EU) and worldwide developed by specialized institutions with respect to apparel industry status and trends, and a research on the websites of the top 10 CAD suppliers of software products dedicate for apparel industrial segment.

Findings/Results: *The paper shows that the software solutions suppliers should involve customers and local distributors in the development process to ensure their relevance and to remain successful on the market.*

It is also highlighting the importance of total employee commitment in the product development process.

Practical Implications: The study helps to understand the relevance of applying the TQM model in the process of developing software products for industrial domains such as apparel industry.

Originality/Value: *There are relatively few studies focusing on the development of dedicated software solutions for the apparel industry and on the particularities of the sector that are influencing the software development trends.*

Thus, the value of this article comes from the interpretation of the TQM model applied to software solution development for apparel industry.

Keywords: *product development, globalization, customization, emerging markets, new business model, total management*

Introduction

Almost fifty years of data available made possible comparisons between the performance of countries under a liberalized versus a non-liberalized regime. According to Stanford University researchers Wacziarg and Welch (2003), in 1960, „just 22 percent of all countries, representing just 21 percent of the global population, had open trade policies, in the sense defined by Sachs and Warner (1995). By 2000, some 73 percent of countries, representing 46 percent of the world’s population, were open to international trade”. Same authors concluded that trade liberalization has, on average, robust positive effects on growth, openness and investment rates within countries. “The removal of trade barriers such as import tariffs, export duties and quantitative restrictions stimulated the growth of exports and imports” (Kassim, 2015).

In 2001, Werner Stengg - an official of the Enterprise Directorate-General of the European Commission, anticipated that „the removal of all quantitative import restrictions in 2005 will have major implications on global trade flows in T/C (textile and clothing) products”. Offshoring and outsourcing models that

emerged with trade liberalization after 2005 produced important growth in the textile industry in Asian countries and other parts of the developing world.

Trade liberalization came together with the liberalization of international capital markets, of the migration of the workforce. international agreements and conventions for the protection of property rights (including intellectual property rights related to proprietary knowledge). The outcome of these liberalizing and integrating processes is known as globalization (Hillman, 2008).

According to the International Labor Office (2019) "technological advances, climate change, globalization and changing demographics" are the four elements that "will shape industries in the future".

The positive, and particularly the negative implications brought by globalization were never entirely foreseeable. In the textile industry all these changes lead to the flooding of the clothing market, and to its saturation with cheap and inferior quality products. Consumers became more critical when accepting a product, preoccupied with details that are not related to the quality or the pricing of the actual product - such as the supply chain that had been involved into the manufacturing process of the article - all before deciding to make the purchase. They also started expecting the product to represent their personality and to make them feel unique. Recent studies (International Labor Office, 2019) confirm that the production and trade of clothing is decelerating in terms of volumes and directing attention to quality and customization.

Climate change is expected to have wide-ranging effects throughout textiles, clothing, leather and footwear (TCLF) global supply chains (ILO, 2019). "While the effects of a changing climate are beginning to affect the industries, it is arguably governments' green growth policies, consumers' demands for sustainability, and civil society organizations' concerns about the environmental footprint of the industries that have so far spurred the greatest action among brands, manufacturers, and producers of raw materials to adopt new technologies, business models and production processes to protect the environment and limit the industries' contribution to global warming and its related effects (...) Nevertheless, these approaches and production processes can be costly to develop and implement, especially for developing countries and for small and medium-sized enterprises(SMEs), which is reflected in the relatively slow uptake of green and clean technology and business models in the industries to date (...) and while these have shown promise and potential, they have yet to be brought to scale. At the current rate, it will take many years before the TCLF industries move to a circular economy approach and become truly sustainable", the ILO report mentions.

With regards to demography, ILO believes that" shifting demographics will continue to drive changes in the industries in the future. This includes but is not limited to: a growth in the global population, an increase in the number of female and male middle-class consumers, a transformation in the age structure across regions and countries, and changes in consumer preferences and demand."

With the development of new technologies and the endless potential of robotics and automation to increase productivity, a process of re- or nearshoring of production is likely. „In the past few years, however, the debate has increasingly shifted to the potentially much greater impact that digitalization will have across TCLF supply chains, with critical implications for a range of occupations and tasks in the industries, not only in manufacturing but also in design, marketing, finance, logistics, and retail." (ILO, 2019, p. 2).

The producers of new technologies need to understand the world is at a major crossroads, to drive change instead of merely react, and to develop new products that are relevant and effective. And, not the least, to develop solutions that meet both the needs and the interests of customers.

Success Factors for New Product Development

There are many models which attempt to describe the factors which influence the development of successful products. One such model is that of Cooper et al. (1995) which establishes that the factors for new product performance are: the NPD process, the NPD strategy, the organization, the culture and the management commitment. The model proposed by Cooper however was criticized for failing" to acknowledge the role of knowledge and other non-technical components of innovation" (Leonard et al, 1998 apud Joubert&VanBelle, 2012).

Marketing researchers Montoya-Weiss and Calantone (1994) propose a different categorization of success factors: strategic factors, market factors, development process factors and organizational factors.

Strategic factors include:

- Product advantage (customer's perception of product superiority with regards to quality, cost-benefit ratio or function) relative to competitors.
- Marketing synergy (how well the needs of the project and the firm's resources and skills fit together, with respect to salesforce, distribution, advertising, promotion, market research and customer service);
- Technological synergy (the coherence between the needs of the project and the firm's resources and skills in the area of product development, engineering and production);
- Strategy (the original impulse for the development of a project - defensive, reactive, proactive, imitative; how well does the new product fit with the firm's strategy);
- Company resources (the compatibility of resources of the firm with the requirement of the project - capital, manufacturing facilities, manpower);

Market factors are:

- Market potential (size and growth of the market, customer need for the product type - the importance of the product to the customer);
- Market competitiveness (the intensity of the competition in the marketplace - in general or with regards to price, quality, service, salesforce or distribution);
- Environment (the general operating environment in which the firm operates - risks, legal framework etc.)

Development process factors are:

- Protocol (the firm's knowledge and understanding of the market they operate in, technical conditions to be met prior to product development - customer needs, interests, product concept, specifications and requirements etc.);
- Proficiency of predevelopment activities (initial market analysis, technical assessment, business and financial analysis);
- Proficiency of market-related activities (marketing research, customer tests of prototypes/samples, service, advertising, market launch);
- Proficiency of technological activities (proficiency of product development, in-house testing, pilot production, production start-up and obtaining necessary technology)
- Top management support, control and skills (the top management's commitment to the project, day-to-day involvement, guidance/direction, control over the project development, product champions/key individuals);
- Speed to market (the speed of the development/launch effort, launch timing, development timing cycle, first or second market effects);
- Costs (project development costs, measures of production, research and development, marketing costs overruns, measures related to insufficient project funds);
- Financial/business analysis (the proficiency of ongoing financial and business analysis during development, prior to commercialization and full-scale launch, measures of go/no go decisions);

Organizational factors include:

- Internal/external communication (coordination and cooperation within the firm and with other firms);
- Organizational factors (organizational structure of the firm, by project - teams, new venture, organizational climate, size, centralization, reward structure, job design).

Trends in apparel industry: mass customization

Inherently, trends in apparel industry are also influenced by the global megatrends: globalization, climate change, demographics and technology advances. The producers of cloths are forced to rethink the way the garments have been created until now and many of them are already looking to reorient their production to emerging markets.

In 2017, the EC (European Commission) JRC (Joint Research Center) organized an event with the purpose of facilitating the understanding of the long-term needs and challenges faced by European textile and clothing industry, based on case-studies. According to the *Textiles and Clothing Manufacturing: Vision for 2025 and Actions Needed* Report, “the European textile sector still represents 2.4% of EU manufacturing employment and 1.4% of EU manufacturing value added. It is also mostly made up of SMEs (Small and medium sized enterprises) widely distributed across many Member States.” (2017). The key conclusion of the event was that by 2025, this industry sector will “operate according to a globalized and efficient circular economic model that maximizes the use of local resources, exploits advanced manufacturing techniques and engages in cross-sectorial collaborations and strategic clusters”. Four clusters have been identified: Innovation - in this area the focus has been pointed to emerging markets, especially to customized production; Resources - focus on reusing the textiles, traceability of materials and total support for recycling; Trade and Skills.

Corroborating the conclusions from the EC JRC Report with the situation described by ILO (2019) which highlights the fact that there is “a general slowdown of trade in manufactured goods, world textile and apparel trade is decelerating” we can conclude that the feature in the clothing and apparel industry belongs to a different type of product manufacturing which will replace or at least balance the mass production.

The alternative to mass production is mass customization. According to Pan (2012), there are six levels of customization: the ‘Basic Customizer’, the ‘Alteration Customizer’, the ‘Cosmetic Customizer’, the ‘Transparent Customizer’, the ‘Self-Adaptive Customizer’ and the ‘Collaborative Customizer’. Each of these levels of customization treats a different segment of customization, and their complexity is in direct relation with the level of relationship engagement between Producers and customers. As the level of customization increases, customers’s involvement moves further upstream of the supply chain (Lampel & Mintzberg, 1996; Blecker & Abdekafit, 2006).”

TQM Concept and benefits

In the context of an industry with an upward and unpredictable shifting trend, the technology suppliers must remain constantly connected to market trends so that they can offer solutions that respond to the new needs.

Total Quality Management (TQM) is a customer-oriented management approach that held up very well over time. In his book *Total Quality Management Key Concepts and Case studies*, Kiran (2017) explains that all definitions given to TQM by quality organizations such as British Standard Institution Standard BS7850-1:1992, the American Society of Quality, ISO (International Organization of Standardization) 9000 etc. or by acknowledged authors such Deming, Juran and Crosbi “focus on the efforts put in by organizations to fulfill customer requirements” (Kiran, 2017).

Looking into the way the ISO defines the TQM, we can identify the following elements as being involved in the process from the TQM specific paradigms:

TOTAL: all functions (design, production, marketing, purchase, maintenance, quality control, HR); all levels (Chairman and Managing Director, General Manager, Supervision, Operator); all persons having a stake (Factory personnel, Corporate office, Shareholders, Suppliers).

QUALITY: customer satisfaction, customer driven, functional requirement of the product, product specifications, process parameters.

MANAGEMENT: effective direction, monitoring and control; continuous improvements, effective utilization of resources, executive commitment, well-planned and effective decision making, employee empowerment.

TQM is basically a change of state of mind from product oriented (result-oriented) to customer centricity.

According to Besterfield et al. (2012) TQM relies on six basic concepts:

- A committed and involved management to provide long-term top-to-bottom organizational support.
- An unwavering focus on the customer, both internally and externally.
- Effective involvement and utilization of the entire workforce.
- Continuous improvement of the business and production process.
- Treating suppliers as partners.
- Establish performance measures for the processes.

The benefits of the TQM derive from its concepts and principles. Following the list of basic concepts listed above we can easily deduct at list four major benefits of TQM: improved product quality due to committed and involved management, customer satisfaction and profitability due to focus on customer needs, business sustainability due to continuous improvement and constant utilization of the entire workforce and employee motivation.

The core technology that is expected to be widely implemented for improving and optimizing the textile and clothing industry sector as the Textiles and Clothing Manufacturing: Vision for 2025 and Actions Needed report developed by European Commission shows is the software technology. Moheel et al. (2019) have made a review of CSFs (Critical Success Factors) of TQM in software development articles published between 1989 -2017, based on a list of relevant selected keywords. They have found a list of twenty different CFSs. The first three most relevant TQM CFSs for software development have been proved to be: Top Management Commitment and Leadership; Human Resource Management and Employee Empowerment; customer focus and process quality management. This finding from their research can prove that TQM should be considered as one of the best forms of management for software development in the current textile market.

Conclusions

Industries are shaped by “technological advances, climate change, globalization and changing demographics” (ILO, 2019), factors which influence each other as well. Technology developers need to adopt new technologies, business models and production processes to protect the environment, which in turn (particularly digitalization) will have critical implications for a range of occupations and tasks in the industries.

Mass customization – seen as the opposite of mass production - is a model which plays well in the global, yet so personally defined world. Mass customization production uses the benefits of globalization while alleviating the negative outcomes. The long-term effects of the new trend in the apparel industry of shifting from mass production to mass customization means that garments manufacturers need to rethink strategic factors, market factors, development process and organizational factors and to start looking for alternative solutions and for new technologies that fits better for the customized products market, as globalization influences supply chains of TCLF.

Total Quality Management is an opportune and successful management approach aligned to current industry trends. TQM takes into account all of the product development success factors, while producing the needed change of state of mind from product oriented (result-oriented) to customer centricity.

As far as it concerns the technology suppliers for this sector, they have to remain in constant connection with the manufacturers for quickly identifying the new “jobs to be done” (Ulwick, 2016) and for bringing adapted solutions for the new manufacturing production needs. This interconnection and communication relation type must be a “continuous game” (Carse, 1986).

References

Akgun, A.E., Byrne J.C., Lynn G.S. and Keskin H.

2007

"New product development in turbulent environments: Impact of improvisation and unlearning on new product performance". In *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 203–230, Elsevier, Amsterdam.

Pan, B.

2012

"A Mass Customisation Implementation Model For The Total Design Process Of The Fashion System" In *IGI Global Fashion Supply Chain Management: Industry & Business Analysis*, IGI Global, Hershey, Penn., USA DOI: 10.4018/978-1-60960-756-2.ch014.

Besterfield, D.H., Besterfield-Michna, C., Besterfield, G.H., Besterfield-Sacre, M., Urdhwareshe, H. and Urdhwareshe, R.

2012

"Total Quality Management", Revised 3rd Edition, University Series, Pearson Education, Delhi-Chennai-Chandigarh, ISBN 9788131764961, eISBN 9788131776308.

Biggemann, S., Kowalkowski, C., Maley, J. and Brege, S.

2013

"Development and implementation of customer solutions: A study of process dynamics and market shaping". In *Industrial Marketing Management*, vol. 42, Issue 7, 1083-1092, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2013.07.026>

Carse, J.P.

1986

"Finite and infinite games. A vision of life as play and possibility". The Free Press, Macmillan, Inc., New York.

Dikert, K., Paasivaara, M. and Lassenius C.

2015

"Challenges and success factors for large-scale agile transformations: A systematic literature review". In *The Journal of Systems and Software*, Vol. 119, 87-108, Elsevier, Amsterdam.

Hillman A.

2008

"Trade Liberalization and Globalization". In *Readings in Public Choice and Constitutional Political Economy*. Springer, Boston, MA. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-75870-1_27

International Labour Office

2019

"The future of work in textiles, clothing, leather and footwear". In Working Paper No.326. International Labour Office, Sectoral Policies Department, Geneva.

Joubert, J. and Van Bell, J.P.

2012

"Success Factors for Product and Service Innovation: a Critical Literature Review and Proposed Integrative Framework". In *Management Dynamics, Vol 12 No 2, 1-22*, Jaipuria Institute of Management, Lucknow.

Kassim L.

2015

"The Impact of Trade Liberalization on Export Growth and Import Growth in Sub-Saharan Africa". In Ncube M., Faye I., Verdier-Chouchane A. (eds) *Regional Integration and Trade in Africa*. Palgrave Macmillan, London. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137462053_4

Kiran, D.R.

2017

"Total Quality Management: Key Concepts and Case Studies". BSP Books PVT. Ltd. published by Elsevier Inc., India, ISBN 978-0-12-8111035-5.

Lindsjörn, Y., Sjøberga, D.I.K., Dingsøyr, T., Bergersena, G.R. and Dybå, T.

2016

"Teamwork quality and project success in software development: A survey of agile development teams". In *Journal of Systems and Software*, Vol. 122, 274-286, Elsevier, Amsterdam, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2016.09.028>.

Moheel, B., Alkatheri, S., AISukhayri, A. and AbdulAziz, A.

2019

"Critical Success Factors of Total Quality Management in Software Development". In International Advanced Research Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 6, Issue 2, Chennai, ISSN (Online) 2393-8021/ISSN (Print) 2394-1588.

Montoya-Weiss and M.M, Calantone, R.

1994

"Determinants of new product performance: A review and meta-analysis". In Journal of Product Innovation Management, Vol. 11, Issue 5, 397-417, Elsevier, Amsterdam.

Smolander, K., Ovaska, P. and Juvonen, P.

2006

"Local software development in industry globalization", ECIS 2006 Proceedings. 108, <https://aisel.aisnet.org/ecis2006/108>

Stengg, W.

2001

"The textile and clothing industry in the EU. A survey". In Enterprise Papers No. 2 – 2001. Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, ISBN 92-894-1280-1.

Subburaj, R.

1997

"Software Quality Triangle for Total Quality Management". Prezentat la IETE Symposium, Thiruvananthapuram.

Ulwick, A.W.

2016

"Jobs To Be Done Theory to Practices", IDEA BITE PRESS ISBN 978-0-9905767-5-4

Wanderley, M., Menezes, J., Gusmão and C., Lima, F.

2015

"Proposal of Risk Management Metrics for Multiple Project Software Development". In Procedia Computer Science, Volume 64, 1001-1009, Elsevier, Amsterdam, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.08.619>

Wacziarg, R., Horn Welch, K.

2003

"Trade Liberalization And Growth: New Evidence". Working Paper 10152. National Bureau Of Economic Research, Cambridge, Mass.

Webography

<https://www.smartsheet.com/total-quality-management> (accessed on 1 May 2020)

<https://shenglufashion.com/2020/04/13/eu-textile-and-apparel-industry-and-trade-patterns-updated-april-2020/> (accessed on 1 May 2020)

<https://www.managementstudyguide.com/total-quality-management.htm> (accessed on 2 May 2020)